

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF TRANSFORMATION OF CULTURAL PROCESSES.

Ulugbek SAFAROV

The Central Council of the Milliy tiklanish

Democratic Party

Annotation: this leads to a change, transformation of cultural processes in a globalizing world. In the process of transformation, the worldview, consciousness, thinking, and attitude of young people to life have been radically updated, this is not an exaggeration. But this is the urgent task of the day - to find an answer to the question of what these changes are, what is the important factor and the specifics of the "new" views that we emphasize.

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It is the reality of today's world that transformation processes have wide possibilities as a natural process that goes along with the development of society, and its use for various purposes has increased. Life itself demands that in these processes, educating young people who can think independently based on our national values, who have a healthy worldview, who are able to resist any ideological threats, who are strong-willed and highly spiritual, is gaining priority.

As we all know, the constant acceleration of the pace of life has led to the transformation of cultural processes to one degree or another. The global era, along with providing unlimited opportunities to the whole world, also creates global problems. In the essence of cultural processes, we can see such things as the clash of civilizations, different worldviews of different people, and the rise of relations between social values to a new, unique level.

In the process of transformation, young people's worldview, consciousness, thinking, and attitude to life were fundamentally renewed, this is not an

exaggeration. However, it is an urgent daily task to find an answer to the question of what are the important factors and uniqueness of these changes, the "new" views that we emphasize. In the context of the transformation of cultural processes in the process of globalization, the issue of youth morality has been researched and is being done by a number of scientists.

The processes of globalization and the transformation of cultural processes are interdependent and mutually demanding realities. The term globalization was first coined by the American scientist T. It was used by Levitt in his 1983 article in the Harvard Business Review. In particular, globalization is recognized as an economic concept, that is, the process of unification of various regional product markets produced by transnational corporations. Since then, different approaches to the concept of globalization have continued.

If we pay attention to the essence of "transformation", transformation [lat. *transformatio* – re-transformation, re-formation (in genetics)] – a change in its genetic characteristics as a result of foreign DNA entering the cell; It is one of the methods of genetic material exchange in prokaryotes. From these concepts, it is known that the concept of transformation entered science primarily as a genetic and biological concept. The wide use of information in the information society, the sharp increase in demand for it, leads to the unification of everyone in the global information space. This combination, in turn, changes the life of society, especially cultural processes. Here we think it is better to use the term transformation. In particular, the transformation of cultural processes is not a revolution or a big change. It is a process of regular change of existing culture as a result of invisible elements of another culture. As we noted above, this concept is considered a genetic, biological concept, and a certain virus enters the body and changes this organism from the inside. But this change was not felt outside. Globalization processes, first of all, create the ground for the transformation of cultural processes, and the exchange of cultures begins to take place in society.

A process is an event in the development of something, a change of

circumstances one after the other, a process is a set of successive actions to achieve a result. The concept of cultural process reflects science, art, and culture. In these processes, it will be possible to preserve the originality of culture and national identity by raising the national value and national-spiritual heritage. Globalization and transformation processes represent the formation of a completely new economic, social-political, natural-biological global environment and, at the same time, the transformation of existing national and regional problems into global problems. It should be noted that globalization is a process that is directly related to the intensification of socio-political and economic life. This is a new stage of social development, and its emergence was possible only thanks to scientific and technical achievements. It consists of many profound changes taking place in various spheres of human activity. These changes reflect the transformation of cultural processes.

There are several reasons why globalization has become so important today: the rapid development of technology, the facilitation of communication and information exchange, political processes such as the fall of communism, the increase in the volume of international cargo transportation due to the development of transportation, and the development of tourism. This, in turn, created an opportunity for companies to develop, led to the opening of additional markets, expanded consumption types as a result of the integration of culture and values, increased competition in the international market, opened new sources of raw materials and expanded the investment process.

In short, globalization causes the transformation of cultural processes. Because its characteristics of happening in space and time are different, new possibilities are manifested in the influence it has on the world change. It is appropriate to recognize the concept of globalization as a characteristic that creates the transformation of cultural processes. Of course, the issue of the impact of the transformation of cultural processes on young people is one of the most urgent and important problems of today. We intend to focus on this in the next releases.